

INTERACTIVE EDUCATIONAL METHODS AND PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL REQUIREMENTS FOR THEIR IMPLEMENTATION

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Annotation: in this article, the forms of interactive education and pedagogical-psychological requirements for their effective implementation. Types of debates, the method of conducting a written debate, discussion in the lesson, breinshtorming and the technology of conducting trainings, meîodes of active teaching and their organization. interactive educational methods and their socio-psychological characteristics. Socio-psychological conditions for working with an audience. Application of interactive methods in the educational process. there is talk about samples from interactive educational methods.

Keywords: approach, pedagogical technology, interactive methods, education

Currently, modern methods of teaching are widely used in the educational process. The application of modern teaching methods leads to the achievement of high efficiency in the teaching process. The choice of educational methods based on the didactic task of each lesson is considered appropriate.

While maintaining the traditional lesson form, enriching it with techniques that activate the activities of different learners leads to an increase in the level of assimilation of the learner. To do this, it is required to rationally organize the lesson process, to gain the interest of the educator in training, to constantly stimulate their activity in the educational process, to independently perform the practical exercise of education, such as mental attack, work in small groups, controversy, problem situation, directing text, Project, role-playing, when opening the educational material into small pieces.

These techniques are also called interactive or interactive methods. Interactive methods are understood as those that activate and motivate learners to think independently, and promote the effectiveness of learning at the heart of the educational process.

Interdisciplinary-occurs in teacher and student communication. The main goal of taking a lesson using interactive techniques is to create an environment for the creative, active, free thinking of the student by creating favorable conditions and situations for the educational process. The role of the teacher in the application of interactive methods in the educational process is incomparable. When choosing interactive methods, the teacher should pay attention to:

- to be closely related to the method of teaching, methods of teaching activities;
- that the cooperation of the teacher and the student must be reflected in achieving the goal;
- to the individual psychological nature of students;
- to the consistency and systemativeness of the information being given.

Currently, widely used interactive methods serve to improve the quality of Education. These are techniques such as: mental cell, gross mental cell, cluster, decision cell, zig-zag, black box, 6x6x6, BBB, sinkwein, Carpenter, venn diagram.

When these methods are used in the educational process:

- careful assimilation of certain theoretical knowledge;
- to make good use of time;
- to the formation of free thinking of students;
- to the active participation of each student in the course of the lesson;
- to be able to listen to the opinion of others;
- to be able to defend his opinion;
- the skill of being able to summarize the points expressed leads to the formation.

The psychological essence of the interactive method is that in a simple discussion, debaters try to state a more conscious, well-founded thinking. In doing so, the debaters are given the opportunity to express whatever thought is poured into the brain, free without criticism or justification, "whatever comes to the language", but in turn. This thing is more accessible in conditions where the problem is much more unfamiliar, the question is complex or ambiguous. That is, in this, "free associations" are allowed, and ultimately the group itself separates a certain rational, „maggot".

Technology of discussion, breinshtorming and training in the lesson.

There is another form of debating that gives its name in Russian as "mozgovaya Ataka", in English as "brain storming".

In our language, there is no clear analogy of this concept, but it can be called an "attack on the brain" or a "clash of thoughts", a "battle of thoughts field". This method was first used by the American scientist A.Ogbom had proposed it as early as the 30s and had achieved a certain achievement in planning a major project using this method and predicting its results in advance. But later experts began to express the opinion that it is possible to apply it only when discussing tasks with a non-standard, specific solution, however, there are many practical advantages of fully organized breinshtorming. Only in this it is necessary to adhere to the following rules::

- sentences should be very short, the connection does not have to be justified;
- any sentence or opinion cannot be criticized, that is, opinions are from criticism;
- more important than logical thoughts is the thought that arose in the brain by chance, from Fantastic or unglates;
- an opinion or a short comment expressed will be recorded;
- the thought or ideas expressed are not distinguished as those of this or that participant, that is, they are-without an author;
- the choice of opinion or good idea is made by individual "critics" or informal leaders of the groupnig.

Interactive methods are also significant in that the teacher will never sharply reject the student's opinion, but will only tell the correct conclusion from time to time. As a result, the student realizes his mistake himself. This prevents them from making mistakes such as being depressed, braking in thinking. Interactive methods are based on mutual respect between the teacher and the student. The teacher, in any case, listens to the student's opinion and expresses respect. With this, it trains students to listen to each other. Suffixes are expressed through words such as" adding to your opinion", " we also have some opinions". In a lesson organized in this way, the student feels self-esteem. In such conditions, without any taizik begins to think freely and can openly state it. Together with this, he learns to respect others.

Intaerfaol methods provide constant activity in students. Students do not stay idle during the course of the lesson, they are busy with some problem related to the relevant topic. As a result, students do not engage in extracurricular activities.

Interactive methods are manifested in the interaction of the teacher – student and students. The main goal of interactive methods is to create an environment for active and free thinking of the student by creating the most favorable situation for the educational process. The organization of the last lesson on the basis of interactive methods is such that in this process, not a single student will be left out, that is, they will have the opportunity to openly express what they know, what they think.

Currently, in the educational process, students are required to train them in free and independent thinking, in conjunction with their knowledge. Young people with Zero independent thoughts love the motherland, the mother has a conscious attitude towards nature, looks with hope for the future. When composing these qualities in students, it is important to use interactive techniques. When organizing the educational process, it is advisable to use training in the formation of educational and educational work between the teacher and the student, as well as in the formation of creative abilities.

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